

**PHYSICOCHEMICAL, HEAVY METALS AND HYDROCARBONS
STUDY OF SURFACE WATER AND SEDIMENT FROM ALAPE RIVER
AND ITS WATERSHED IN IGBOKODA, SOUTH-WEST NIGERIA.**

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ABSTRACT

Physicochemical, heavy metals and hydrocarbon parameters of fifteen surface water samples and fourteen sediment samples from the Alape River and its watershed in Igbokoda, South-Western Nigeria have been analysed. APHA and ASTM standard methods were employed in the analysis of the samples while obtained results were compared to DPR, NESREA, NSDWQ and WHO set standards. The mean pH values of the River and its watershed were found to be 6.78 and 7.25 respectively, falling within the recommended limit. In terms of DO, the mean values of 5.25 mg/L and 5.42 mg/L obtained were equally within the acceptable range for supporting aquatic organisms. Mean values of TS and salinity were relatively low, indicating favourable conditions. However, the mean total hardness value was considerably high. The River and its watershed exhibited low levels of O&G, TPH, and Cl⁻. The presence of organic matter was also observed, as demonstrated from the mean values of BOD and COD, suggesting some level of pollution. Furthermore, the sediments from the River contained detectable concentrations of some heavy metals; Fe, Pb, Cu, Mn, and Zn. The concentration of Fe exceeded the recommended limit set by NESREA. Overall, the research outcomes serve as valuable baseline data for future studies and offer insights to establish effective measures to prevent pollution in the event of industrialization in the area.

Keyword: (Alape River, Sediment, Hydrocarbons, Heavy Metals and Physicochemical parameters)

INTRODUCTION

The study of surface water and sediment quality is of utmost importance in understanding the ecological health and potential risks associated with aquatic ecosystems. Water is a vital resource that sustains life on Earth, and its quality plays a crucial role in the overall health of ecosystems and human populations [1,2,3]. In Nigeria, a country located in West Africa, surface water bodies, such as rivers and lakes, serve as primary sources of freshwater for various purposes, including drinking, irrigation, fishing,

and transportation. However, these water bodies are increasingly vulnerable to contamination due to anthropogenic activities, such as urbanization, industrialization, and agricultural practices [4,5]. As a result, it becomes essential to conduct baseline studies to assess the quality of surface water and sediment in order to understand the existing pollution levels and potential risks associated with aquatic ecosystems. One of such water bodies in Nigeria is the Alape River, situated in the Igbokoda, South-West

geographical region of the country. The Alape River and its surrounding watershed are of great significance to the local communities, as they provide water resources for domestic use, agricultural activities, and other livelihood needs. However, with the increasing population, possible industrialisation, and intensifying agricultural practices in the area, concerns have arisen regarding the potential contamination of the Alape River and its watershed. Various pollutants, including heavy metals, pesticides, nutrients, and organic compounds, can enter water bodies through runoff, industrial discharges, and improper waste disposal [6,7,8]. These pollutants can have detrimental effects on the aquatic ecosystem, leading to the degradation of water quality, loss of biodiversity, and a decline in ecosystem services. Additionally, the contamination of surface water and sediment can pose serious risks to human health, as these water bodies are often used for drinking and domestic purposes [9,10,11,12]. Therefore, it becomes imperative to conduct a comprehensive baseline study to evaluate the current state of water and sediment quality in the Alape River and its watershed.

The primary objective of this research is to conduct a thorough baseline study of the surface water and sediment in the Alape River and its watershed in Igbokoda, Nigeria. This study aims to assess various parameters, including physicochemical characteristics, nutrient levels, heavy metal concentrations, and hydrocarbons pollutant content in water and sediment samples

collected from different locations within the river and its surrounding watershed. The data collected will provide valuable insights into the current quality status of the Alape River, help identify potential pollution sources, and facilitate the development of effective management strategies. This research will contribute to the existing body of knowledge on water and sediment quality in Nigeria. Therefore, the outcomes of this study will not only benefit the local communities and policymakers in the Igbokoda region but also add to the scientific literature, addressing the gaps in understanding the environmental health of Nigerian water bodies. The research findings can serve as a foundation for further studies and help in designing more focused research projects to address specific pollution concerns or assess the efficacy of remediation measures. Ultimately, the findings of this study will contribute to the preservation and conservation of the Alape River and its watershed, ensuring the long-term well-being of both the environment and the communities that rely on it.

Study Area

The Alape River and its watershed are of great ecological and socio-economic importance, but they are not without their challenges. The River's location in Igbokoda, Illaje Parish, Ondo state Nigeria, between Latitude 6°16.559 N and 6°20.338 N, and Longitude 4°44.945 E and 4°41.892 E (see Figure 1), exposes it to a tropical wet and dry climate characterized by distinct rainy and dry seasons. The rainy seasons occur

from March to July and from September to November, while the dry seasons span from December to February and from August to September [13]. The fluctuating rainfall patterns, influenced by phenomena like El Niño and La Niña, have a profound impact on the river's water levels and flow rates, shaping the lives of the local community.

With an average annual rainfall of around 1,500 millimetres, the Alape River relies heavily on these precipitation events [13]. The seasonal rains fuel the growth of aquatic plants and support the thriving fish population, which in turn sustains the livelihoods of the local residents. This precious water resource acts as a lifeline for the community and nurtures a diverse array of aquatic life, contributing to the overall ecological health of the region.

Stretching approximately 10 kilometres, the Alape River gracefully meanders its way into the vast Atlantic Ocean. Its serene and translucent waters serve as an idyllic backdrop for

recreational activities like swimming, fishing, and boating. Moreover, the river acts as a vital transportation route, enabling convenient travel between the nearby villages via small boats [13]. The surrounding lush vegetation, particularly the mangrove forests, adds to the river's beauty and ecological significance. These mangroves offer a sanctuary for various wildlife species, including monkeys, birds, and reptiles. Beyond their biodiversity value, the mangroves provide a natural defence against the effects of climate change, safeguarding the shoreline from erosion and rising sea levels.

However, the Alape River is not immune to the pressures of human activities. Sand mining, logging, and improper waste disposal have contributed to pollution and degradation, jeopardizing the water quality and the delicate balance of the aquatic ecosystem. This deterioration poses significant challenges to both the environment and the local population, whose well-being depends on the river's resources.

Fig.1 Map of Nigeria showing sampling location and points

MATERIALS AND METHODS

To analyse the physicochemical properties of surface water and sediment samples from the Alape River and its watershed, standard procedures were followed as recommended by regulatory agencies and standard guidelines. These procedures ensure accuracy and consistency in the analysis of the samples.

Sampling, Collection and Preservation

The sampling methodology and preservation adhered to the standard guidelines outlined in

APHA and ASTM manuals [14,15,16,17,18]. Furthermore, the study area was surveyed using a Garmin eTrex10 GPS device (model GS284) to identify fifteen sampling points. These points were distributed across different locations, with nine along the river and five within the watershed. Additionally, a control sample was collected from a water treatment facility in the community. Spacing the sampling points along the river approximately 1.1 kilometres apart, the remaining points within the watershed were situated between 100 meters and 300 meters from

the riverbank. To collect water and sediment samples, a 2-liter water sampler and a grab sampler were utilized, respectively. At each sampling point, composite water samples were taken from the surface. During water sampling, precautions were taken to prevent contact with the sides and bottom of the sampling points, thus avoiding the detachment of accumulated slime or sludge. For the physiochemical analysis, water and sediment samples were collected in 1-liter plastic bottles and Ziploc bags, respectively. In addition, hydrocarbon analysis samples were collected in wide-mouthed, amber-coloured glass bottles, ensuring they were filled to the brim to avoid headspace and minimize volatilization. The use of amber-coloured glass bottles was specifically chosen to prevent photochemical reactions with the samples.

After sampling at each point, various in-situ parameters were measured, and the samples were preserved accordingly. For the preservation of heavy metals, 1.5 ml of concentrated nitric acid (HNO_3) per litre of sample was used. As for organics, preservation involved adding 1.5 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4) per litre of sample until the pH dropped below 2. Following preservation, the samples were transferred to an insulated cooler containing ice pack at 4°C . This ensured the maintenance of sample integrity during transportation to the laboratory. To maintain proper identification, each sample was appropriately labelled according to its location of collection. Water samples from the Alape River were labelled AR1 to AR9, while sediment

samples were labelled ARD1 to ARD9. Samples collected within the watershed were labelled AW10 to AW14 for water and AWD10 to AWD14 for sediment samples. Additionally, a control sample collected from a water treatment facility within the community was labelled ARWC. Ultimately, after the sampling exercise, a total of fifteen water samples and fourteen sediment samples were collected and promptly shipped to the laboratory for analysis.

Surface Water Analysis

Surface water analysis followed the in-situ parameter guidelines for water outlined in APHA and ASTM manual [19,20,21,22,23,24,25]. To measure the hydrogen ion concentration (pH), a Mettler Toledo pH meter (model El 251302928) was utilized. Furthermore, WinLab data line EC/TDS/salinity/Temperature meter (model RS232) was employed to determine electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), salinity, and temperature (Temp). Additionally, the dissolved oxygen (DO) was measured using a YSI 550A DO meter (model 13k102263), while the turbidity of the water samples was determined using a Hannah turbidity meter (model HI 98730). It's worth noting that the probe of each meter was rinsed with deionised water before taking readings for each sample to prevent cross-contamination.

For the ex-situ analysis of water samples, a comprehensive approach was followed, ensuring accuracy and reproducibility of the results. Acidity and alkalinity were determined using the

APHA method [26,27]. The analysis of chloride (Cl^-) adhered to APHA method [28], while total hardness was determined using APHA guidelines [29]. For total solids (TS), the GenLab G5G26S model oven, following the APHA method [30], was employed. Additionally, the estimation of total suspended solids (TSS) relied on the correlation between TS and TDS calculation ($\text{TS} - \text{TDS} = \text{TSS}$), as outlined in ASTM method [24]. Furthermore, the analysis of phosphate (PO_4^{3-}), sulfate (SO_4^{2-}), and nitrate (NO_3^-) followed the guidelines outlined in APHA method [31,32,33]. The nutrient concentrations were determined using the UV Spec Thermo spectrophotometer (model Genesys 10UV). Bicarbonate (HCO_3^-) and carbonate (CO_3^{2-}) concentrations were determined following the guidelines in APHA method [34], utilizing Microsoft Excel 2016 spreadsheets and specific formulas: $\text{HCO}_3^- = (\text{alkalinity} - 5 * 10^{(\text{pH}-10)}) / (1 + 0.94 * 10^{(\text{pH}-10)})$ and $\text{CO}_3^{2-} = (0.94 * \text{HCO}_3^- * 10^{(\text{pH}-10)})$, respectively. Moreover, the analysis of biological oxygen demand (BOD) adhered to the guidelines in APHA method [35], while chemical oxygen demand (COD) was determined following APHA method [36].

Oil and grease (O&G) measurements were conducted following the guidelines outlined in APHA method [37], while the analysis of total petroleum hydrocarbon (TPH) was performed in accordance with the guidelines outlined in ASTM method [38]. To analyse TPH, an Agilent Gas Chromatograph equipped with a Flame

Ionization Detector (GC/FID) 6890N (model G150N) was used. For the determination of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), the guidelines outlined in APHA method [39] were followed, and an Agilent Gas Chromatograph coupled with a Mass Spectrometer (GC/MS) 720A/5975 (model G4350N) was utilized for the analysis. In addition to PAHs, heavy metal digestion was carried out following the procedures outlined in ASTM and APHA method [40,41]. The concentrations of the aliquots for the metals of interest, including iron (Fe), lead (Pb), copper (Cu), cadmium (Cd), nickel (Ni), chromium (Cr), manganese (Mn), and zinc (Zn), were determined according to the procedures outlined in APHA method [42]. For the analysis of heavy metals, an Agilent atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS) (model G8430A) was employed. Through adherence to these comprehensive guidelines and standardized protocols, the study ensured accurate and reliable analysis of water samples. Each step was meticulously followed, employing advanced instruments and methodologies to provide a thorough assessment of the water quality parameters, nutrients, hydrocarbons, and heavy metals present in the samples.

Sediments Analysis

To prepare the sediment samples for analysis, the guidelines outlined in ASTM method [43,44] were followed. The samples were air-dried in the laboratory until they reached a constant weight. Then, using a ceramic mortar and pestle, the dried

samples were ground and passed through a 2-millimeter mesh sieve. Careful removal of any uncrushable pebbles or solid materials ensured the purity of the samples, and with these steps completed, the samples were ready for analysis.

Various guidelines and procedures were followed to ensure accurate results for the chemical analyses. The pH of the sediment samples was determined according to the guidelines in ASTM method [45]. For the measurement of total organic carbon (TOC), ASTM method [46] was employed. Additionally, the nutrient test followed the guidelines outlined in APHA method [31,32,33] with the aliquots of the sediments utilized for the analysis. The same UV Spec instrument used for water analysis was employed here.

Subsequently, the digestion of the sediment for heavy metal analysis adhered to the specifications outlined in ASTM method [47]. The concentration of the metals was determined using the guidelines outlined in APHA method [42]. It's worth noting that the atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS) instrument used for water analysis was also utilized for the measurement of heavy metal concentrations in the sediment samples. To measure the total petroleum hydrocarbon (TPH) and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in the sediment samples, the procedures outlined in ASTM method [48,49] were followed. The same GC instrument used for water analysis was employed for these measurements. Moreover, all solvents and reagents used for the analysis were of analytical

grade and procured from Sigma-Aldrich, ensuring the highest quality standards were maintained throughout the process.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 to Table 3 shows the mean values of multiple parameters associated with water quality while Table 4 to Table 5 shows the mean values of multiple parameters associated with sediment. These values were compared to regulatory standards and relevant literature to facilitate the discussion of the research findings. The Nigerian Standards for Drinking Water Quality, NSDWQ [50], National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency, NESREA [51], Department of Petroleum Resources, DPR [52] and the World Health Organization. WHO [53] Guidelines for Drinking Water Quality were used as regulatory benchmarks.

The mean pH value of the Alape River was 6.78, while its watershed recorded a slightly higher pH of 7.25 (see Table 1). This indicates a very weak acidic nature for Alape River while its watershed indicates a slightly neutral nature, which could be attributed to a variety of factors. Natural processes such as organic decomposition may contribute to this acidity in the river. Also, anthropogenic activities like agricultural runoff could play a role. To evaluate the acceptability of these pH values, regulatory standards were consulted, recommending a pH range of 6.5 to 8.5

[50,51,53]. It is worth noting that the mean pH value obtained in this study falls within the acceptable range provided by the regulatory standards. These findings align with previous research conducted in the region, providing further support for the study's validity. A study in Lagos, Nigeria reported pH values ranging from 5.94 to 7.63 in surface water samples from Tin Can Island [54]. Similarly, another study in Ebonyi, Nigeria found pH values ranging from 6.86 to 7.39 in an investigation of pond water physicochemical characteristics [55]. Additionally, a report from south-eastern Nigeria found pH values ranging from 6.4 to 6.8 in the study of surface water quality in the Mamu River basin [1]. These pH ranges are comparable to the pH value obtained in the Alape River and its watershed, further supporting the consistency of the findings. Moreover, the mean pH value obtained in this study, as well as the control value of 7.53, both fall within the regulatory benchmark

(see Table 1). It is noteworthy that the Alape River and its watershed had mean temperatures of 27.32°C and 27.16°C, respectively (see Table 1). These values align with what is typically expected in tropical regions. WHO [53] recommends a maximum temperature of 25°C to prevent the growth of microorganisms while NESREA [51] recommended a temperature of 40°C (see Table 1). Interestingly, the mean temperature value obtained in this study slightly exceeds the recommended limit by WHO [53]. Furthermore, the study's results revealed that the mean temperature value is consistent with a study conducted in Anambra, Nigeria which recorded a temperature values ranging from 22.00°C to 28.40°C in selected surface water samples from rivers within the state [56]. It is worth noting that the control temperature was found to be 24.8°C, falling within the recommended limit set by regulatory bodies [51,53] (see Table 1).

Table 1: In-situ parameters for water quality in comparison to regulatory standards

Parameters	AR Mean Values	AW Mean Values	ARWC	NESREA Limit for Surface Water	NSDWQ Limit for Drinking Water	WHO Limit for Drinking Water
In-Situ Parameters						
pH	6.78 ± 0.076	7.25 ± 0.160	7.53	6.0-8.5	6.5-8.5	6.5-8.5
Temp. (°C)	27.32 ± 0.291	27.16 ± 0.272	24.8	40	-	25
EC (µS/cm)	37.68 ± 6.970	65.34 ± 20.872	12.10	1,000	1,000	1,500
Turbidity (NTU)	4.90 ± 0.349	3.96 ± 0.582	1.12	10	5	5
Salinity (mg/L)	16.87 ± 3.437	31.76 ± 5.488	32.96	200	-	250

DO (mg/L)	5.25 ± 0.798	5.42 ± 0.542	5.12	≥ 5	≥ 5	≥ 5
TDS (mg/L)	25.26 ± 4.796	49.46 ± 13.650	5.76	500	500	500

In addition, the mean EC value of the Alape River measured at 37.6 μ S/cm, while its watershed recorded a slightly higher value of 65.34 μ S/cm. additionally; both the river and its watershed exhibited TDS values of 25.60 mg/L and 49.46 mg/L, respectively (see Table 1). These measurements indicate the presence of dissolved salts and ions in the water, which can originate from natural sources such as rock weathering or human activities like mining. To assess the acceptability of these values, it is essential to refer to the guidelines set by regulatory bodies [50,51,53]. According to these standards, the recommended limits for EC are 1,000 μ S/cm and 1,500 μ S/cm, while the limit for TDS is 500 mg/L (see Table 1). It is worth noting that the mean values obtained in this study for both conductivity and TDS fall significantly below the limits specified by these guidelines. Supporting the validity of these findings, a study conducted in Ilorin, Nigeria reported similar results for surface water samples collected from the Asa River. In that study, EC values ranged from 82.43 μ S/cm to 275.13 μ S/cm, while TDS values ranged from 44.13 mg/L to 135.00 mg/L [57]. These results further reinforce the consistency of the findings in the current study. Furthermore, the EC and TDS values measured at the control point fell within the regulatory limits, with values of 12.10 μ S/cm and 5.76 mg/L, respectively (see

Table 1). This reinforces the overall quality of the water in both the Alape River and its watershed. The mean turbidity values of 4.90 NTU and 3.96 NTU obtained from the Alape River and its watershed, respectively, indicate low levels of suspended solids in the water. This falls within the acceptable range recommended by regulatory bodies [50,51,53]. The bodies specify a maximum turbidity level of 5 NTU and 10 NTU (see Table 1). Impressively, the control value measured at 1.12 NTU falls well below the limits set by the regulatory standards, indicating excellent water quality. In summary, the EC, TDS, and turbidity measurements obtained from both the Alape River and its watershed demonstrate water quality that meets the regulatory limits. The findings align with previous research and underscore the overall favourable conditions of the water in the studied area.

Subsequently, the mean salinity value of the Alape River was measured at 16.87 mg/L, while its watershed recorded a slightly higher value of 31.76 mg/L. These values fall within the acceptable range of 200 mg/L to 250 mg/L, as recommended by regulatory bodies based on taste threshold rather than health considerations [50,53] (see Table 1). It is fascinating to compare these findings with a study conducted Bayelsa,

Nigeria, where the authors reported a salinity mean value of 8,766.67 mg/L in the Silver River of southern Ijaw [11]. Clearly, the salinity levels observed in the current study are significantly lower. Additionally, the control value of 32.96 mg/L also falls within the regulatory benchmark (see Table 1). It is worth noting that salinity levels can vary due to various factors, including the water source, geological characteristics of the area, and human activities. The mean DO values obtained from the Alape River and its watershed were 5.25 mg/L and 5.42 mg/L, respectively (see Table 1). These values fall within the recommended minimum DO level of 5.0 mg/L set regulatory bodies [50,51,53]. This finding is consistent with other studies conducted around the world. Abdullah [58] conducted a study on the Tigris River in Iraq and reported an average DO level of 5.81 mg/L. The study found that fish diversity and abundance were highest at sites with DO levels above 5.0 mg/L. Similarly, a study conducted on the Shatt al-Arab River in Iran found that fish species richness and diversity were highest at sites with DO levels above 5.0 mg/L. Conversely, DO levels below 3.0 mg/L were associated with fish kills and reduced fish populations [59]. The observed DO value at the control point had a value of 5.12 mg/L, which falls within the regulatory limit. These findings indicate that the Alape River and its watershed maintain adequate DO levels for the thriving of most aquatic organisms.

The study conducted on the surface water of the Alape River and its watershed revealed intriguing findings on acidity and alkalinity. The mean acidity values were determined to be 47.94 mg/L and 47.07 mg/L as CaCO₃, respectively. Notably, these values fall within the recommended limit of 200 mg/L as CaCO₃ [50,51]. On the other hand, the mean alkalinity values for the river and its watershed were measured at 44.48 mg/L and 45.82 mg/L as CaCO₃ (see Table 2). Alkalinity plays a vital role in buffering water against pH changes and supporting aquatic life. It is fascinating to observe that these values align with the recommended limit of 200 mg/L and 600 mg/L as CaCO₃ set by regulatory bodies [50,51,53]. These results are consistent with other studies conducted in the south-western region of Nigeria, which reported acidity values ranging from 5.0 mg/L to 12.0 mg/L as CaCO₃ and alkalinity values ranging from 33.3 mg/L to 78.60 mg/L as CaCO₃ [60]. Further emphasizing the reliability of these findings, the control point exhibited an acidity value of 47.63 mg/L as CaCO₃ and an alkalinity value of 44.69 mg/L as CaCO₃, both falling well below the limits recommended by the regulatory bodies (see Table 2). The total hardness mean values obtained from the Alape River and its watershed were 225.33 mg/L and 227.80 mg/L, respectively. The recommended limit for total hardness are 150 mg/L, 200 mg/L and 500 mg/L respectively [50,51,53]. Additionally, the control value of 108.00 mg/L also falls within the regulatory benchmark (see Table 2). The concentration of

total hardness in the study area can be attributed to the presence of calcium hardness, which is commonly found in surface water sources in Nigeria due to the geological and mineralogical characteristics of the surrounding environment [61]. However, it is crucial to acknowledge that the level of total hardness in the Alape River and its watershed may have negative consequences for water supply and usage. The presence of

hardness can lead to scale formation in pipes and water heaters, resulting in reduced efficiency and increased maintenance costs. Furthermore, elevated levels of total hardness in drinking water can contribute to cardiovascular disease, hypertension, and developmental delays in children [53]. These implications highlight the importance of monitoring and addressing the issue of total hardness in the study area.

Table 2: Chemical parameters for water quality in comparison to regulatory standards

Parameters	AR Mean Values	AW Mean Values	ARWC	NESREA Limit for Surface Water	NSDWQ Limit for Drinking Water	WHO Limit for Drinking Water
Chemical Parameters						
Acidity (mg/L) as CaCO ₃	47.94 ± 1.831	47.07 ± 1.870	36.21	200	200	-
Alkalinity (mg/L) as CaCO ₃	44.48 ± 2.142	45.82 ± 2.365	51.26	600	200	200
Total Hardness (mg/L)	225.33 ± 3.852	227.80 ± 7.040	108.00	500	150	200
HCO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	44.45 ± 2.140	45.72 ± 2.360	51.08	250	-	120
CO ₃ ²⁻ (mg/L)	0.023 ± 0.006	0.082 ± 0.027	0.16	600	-	350
Cl ⁻ (mg/L)	43.67 ± 12.983	39.20 ± 6.246	18.57	350	250	250
SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg/L)	0.60 ± 0.095	0.64 ± 0.097	0.01	500	100	250
PO ₄ ³⁻ (mg/L)	0.58 ± 0.076	0.61 ± 0.111	0.02	3.5	1	1
NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	0.85 ± 0.125	0.81 ± 0.201	0.05	40	50	50
TS (mg/L)	28.28 ± 4.782	53.06 ± 14.21	7.33	500	500	500
TSS (mg/L)	3.04 ± 0.670	3.60 ± 0.579	1.57	100	50	50
BOD (mg/L)	9.69 ± 2.560	7.27 ± 2.099	4.98	6	5	5
COD (mg/L)	50.61 ± 19.144	102.02 ± 9.176	37.96	30	10	10

(-) = Not Applicable

Furthermore, the mean values of HCO₃⁻ were determined to be 44.45 mg/L and 45.72 mg/L, while CO₃²⁻ had values of 0.023 mg/L and 0.082

mg/L, respectively (see Table 2). It is worth noting that HCO₃⁻ is an essential component of natural water and serves as an important indicator

of water quality. On the other hand, CO_3^{2-} plays a significant role in water quality analysis as it influences the pH and alkalinity of water. These values fall within regulatory threshold of 250 mg/L and 120 mg/L for HCO_3^- as well as 600 mg/L and 350 mg/L for CO_3^{2-} respectively [51,53]. Comparing these findings to other studies conducted worldwide, the mean HCO_3^- and CO_3^{2-} values observed in the Alape River and its watershed fall within the range reported in similar studies. A study conducted in Amman city, Jordan reported a value range of 48.76 to 336.18 mg/L for HCO_3^- and 0.012 to 1.91 mg/L for CO_3^{2-} in surface water samples [62]. It is fascinating to observe that the values obtained from this study align with the findings reported. Additionally, another study conducted in Qinghai Lake, China, reported values of 1,360 to 1,860 mg/L for HCO_3^- and 33.8 to 43.9 mg/L for CO_3^{2-} [63]. These ranges provide further context for the concentrations observed in the Alape River and its watershed. The control values for HCO_3^- and CO_3^{2-} in the study were found to be 51.08 mg/L and 0.16 mg/L, respectively, which falls within recommended limit (see Table 2). Chloride (Cl^-) is another crucial parameter in water quality assessment, its concentration significantly affects the taste of water. High levels of Cl^- can be attributed to various human activities such as agricultural runoff, wastewater discharge, and industrial activities. In the Alape River and its watershed, the observed mean Cl^- values were 43.67 mg/L and 39.20 mg/L, respectively. These values indicate a low concentration of Cl^- , posing

minimal risk to human health and aquatic life. Moreover, these values align with the recommended limit of 250 mg/L and 350 mg/L set by regulatory bodies [50,51,53]. Consistency is found with the result obtained from this research, a study conducted on water quality assessment in Ogun River, Nigeria, reported Cl^- levels ranging from 43.60 mg/L to 55.10 mg/L [64]. Similarly, another report on Cl^- levels ranged from 43.80 mg/L to 50.30 mg/L from the same river [2]. It is interesting to note that the Cl^- value at the control point was measured at 18.57 mg/L which falls within the recommended limits by regulatory bodies (see Table 2). Furthermore, these findings provide comprehensive insights into the concentrations of HCO_3^- , CO_3^{2-} , and Cl^- in the Alape River and its watershed. The results showcase the similarities with previous studies conducted worldwide and highlight the overall water quality in the study area. Therefore, it is essential to continuously monitor and assess these parameters to ensure the safety and suitability of water resources for both human and aquatic life. Subsequently, the Alape River and its watershed exhibited relatively low mean values of SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} , and NO_3^- . Specifically, the mean values of SO_4^{2-} were 0.60 mg/L and 0.64 mg/L, while that of PO_4^{3-} were 0.58 mg/L and 0.61 mg/L. Furthermore, the mean values of NO_3^- were 0.85 mg/L and 0.81 mg/L, respectively (see Table 2). These findings indicate that the water source in the Alape River and its watershed is relatively clean in terms of these parameters. It is noteworthy that recommended limits of 100 mg/L,

250 mg/L, and 500 mg/L were for SO_4^{2-} , while that of PO_4^{3-} is 1 mg/L and 3.5 mg/L respectively. Also, NO_3^- limit was recommended at 50 mg/L and 40 mg/L [50,51,53]. The values obtained in the Alape River and their watersheds were well below these recommended limits (see Table 2). Such results provide assurance regarding the water quality in relation to these specific pollutants. When comparing these findings to a study conducted on the water quality of the Oluwa River in southwest Nigeria, noticeable differences emerge. In the Oluwa River, the concentration of SO_4^{2-} was significantly higher at 9.52 mg/L, while the PO_4^{3-} concentration was elevated with a value of 54.92 mg/L. Similarly, the NO_3^- concentration in the Oluwa River was higher, reaching 3.27 mg/L, compared to the Alape River and its watershed [65]. Also, another study on the influence of human activities on the water quality of Ogun River in Nigeria, concentrations of SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} , and NO_3^- were reported as 2.5 mg/L, 0.9 mg/L, and 1.15 mg/L, respectively [3]. It is evident that the levels of SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} , and NO_3^- in the Alape River and its watershed are significantly lower than those observed in these comparative studies. Moreover, the values obtained from the control point for SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} , and NO_3^- were even lower, measuring 0.01 mg/L, 0.03 mg/L, and 0.05 mg/L, respectively (see Table 2). These results further reinforce the notion that contamination with these pollutants is not a significant concern in the study area.

The findings of this study reveal intriguing insights into the levels of particulate matter in the Alape River and its watershed, with a mean TS value of 28.28 mg/L and 53.06 mg/L respectively. It is evident that the water contains relatively low levels of particulate matter. These values, although below the recommended limit of 500 mg/L [50,51,53], may not raise immediate concerns. However, it is crucial to recognize that the TS levels in rivers and water bodies can vary significantly based on various factors, including local geology, land use, and industrial activities. A study conducted in Edo, Nigeria, focused on the Obueyinomo River and reported a TS range of 15.5 to 23.70 mg/L [6], which is considerably lower than the mean value obtained in this study. The authors from the study also highlighted that human activities such as urbanisation and industrialisation tend to elevate TS levels in rivers, emphasizing the importance of monitoring and understanding regional variations. Moreover, the control TS value of 7.33 mg/L in this study falls within the regulatory limits (see Table 2). Also, the mean TSS values for Alape River and its watershed was 3.04 mg/L and 3.60 mg/L respectively. These figures indicate relatively low levels of particulate matter in the water, which are well below the recommended limits of 50 mg/L and 100 mg/L [50,51,53]. Comparing the findings with a study conducted on the Appraisal of Surface Water Quality of Nile River, the authors reported a TSS range of 9.20 to 45.20 mg/L, which is significantly higher than the result obtained from this study [66]. This disparity

highlights the regional variations in TSS levels and the importance of considering specific geographical contexts when interpreting data. Remarkably, the control TSS value of 1.57 mg/L in this study falls comfortably below the recommended limits imposed by regulatory bodies, further affirming the relatively low levels of particulate matter present in the Alape River and its watershed. Thus, the TS and TSS results sheds light on the levels of particulate matter in the Alape River and its watershed, emphasizing their relatively low concentrations. However, it is vital to remain cognizant of the diverse *factors* that influence these levels, such as local geology, land use, and industrial activities.

Nevertheless, the Alape River and its watershed have been closely examined, revealing a concerning presence of organic matter. The mean BOD values of 9.69 mg/L and 7.27 mg/L, while the mean COD values are 50.61 mg/L and 102.02 mg/L respectively, this clearly indicate a certain level of pollution and degradation in water quality (see Table 2). NSDWQ [50] and WHO [53] recommended a limits of 5 mg/L for BOD and 10 mg/L for COD respectively, while NESREA [51] suggests a limit of 6 mg/L for BOD and 30 mg/L for COD (see Table 2). Comparing these guidelines to the mean BOD and COD values from Alape River and its watershed, it becomes apparent that the obtained results exceeded the regulatory limits. To gain further perspective, it is essential to consider other studies conducted worldwide. A study

conducted on river water in Ciparger Cirabon reported BOD values ranging from 0.13 to 1.17 mg/L, which is considerably lower than the values obtained in this study. While the COD values ranged from 118.8 to 138.6 mg/L [67], surpassing the findings of this research. These comparative findings emphasize the severity of the pollution in the Alape River and its watershed. Examining the control point, the BOD and COD values of 4.95 mg/L and 37.96 mg/L, respectively was observed (see Table 2). Notably, the BOD value for the control point falls below the recommended limit, while the COD value for the control point exceeded the recommended limit. Ultimately, the mean BOD and COD results revelled a concerning matter, suggesting that the surface water from the Alape River and its watershed is unsuitable for human consumption without proper treatment. In analysing of O&G and TPH in the Alape River and its watershed, intriguing results were obtained. The mean O&G values were found to be 0.74 mg/L and 0.97 mg/L, while the mean TPH values was 0.02 mg/L and 0.01 mg/L, respectively (see Table 3). It is important to note that the mean O&G value fall significantly below the recommended limits set by regulatory bodies, which is an encouraging finding. The regulatory limit of 5 mg/L, 10 mg/L and 20 mg/L for O&G is surpassed [50,51,52,53], indicating a lack of petroleum hydrocarbon contamination in the Alape River and its watershed. Similarly, the TPH values remain below recommended limit of 0.05 mg/L and 10 mg/L [50,51,52,53]. These results reinforce the

conclusion that the water in this area is free from petroleum pollutants. Additionally; an absence of PAHs was detected during the study, further confirming the absence of contamination. These findings align with other studies that have reported similarly low concentrations of O&G and TPH in surface waters. A study conducted in

the Niger Delta region of Nigeria revealed TPH values ranging from 0.08 mg/L to 2.32 mg/L in surface water from the Imirigi oil field facility [68]. Likewise, another study conducted in the same region reported O&G values ranging from 0.001 mg/L to 0.015 mg/L in drinking water from oil-bearing communities [12].

Table 3: Hydrocarbons and heavy metal parameters for water quality in comparison to regulatory standards

Parameters	AR Mean Values	AW Mean Values	ARWC	NESREA Limit for Surface Water	NSDWQ Limit for Drinking Water	WHO Limit for Drinking Water	DPR Limit for Surface Water
Hydrocarbons and Heavy Metals Parameters							
O&G (mg/L)	0.74 ± 0.268	0.97 ± 0.278	<0.01	10	5	5	20
TPH (mg/L)	0.02 ± 0.010	0.01 ± 0.006	BDL	0.05	0.05	0.05	10
PAHs (mg/L)	BDL	BDL	BDL	0.05	0.0001	0.0001	0.075
Fe (mg/L)	12.40 ± 2.073	9.86 ± 1.270	6.90	0.3	0.3	0.3	-
Pb (mg/L)	BDL	BDL	BDL	0.01	0.01	0.01	-
Cu (mg/L)	0.53 ± 0.161	0.37 ± 0.134	BDL	1.5	1	2	-
Cd (mg/L)	BDL	BDL	BDL	0.05	0.03	0.003	-
Ni (mg/L)	BDL	BDL	BDL	0.03	0.02	0.02	-
Cr (mg/L)	BDL	BDL	BDL	0.05	0.05	0.05	-
Mn (mg/L)	BDL	BDL	BDL	0.5	0.5	0.5	-
Zn (mg/L)	0.67 ± 0.154	0.25 ± 0.122	BDL	3	3	5	-

(-) = Not Applicable

It is worth noting that the concentrations of TPH and PAHs from the control point were below the instrument detection limit (BDL), indicating an exceptionally clean sample. Furthermore, the O&G concentration in the control point was less

than 0.01 mg/L (see Table 3). These findings provide robust evidence that the Alape River and its watershed are relatively clean, lacking significant petroleum pollutants. As a result, the water in this area can be deemed suitable for

various purposes, including industrial use, irrigation, and supporting aquatic life.

Subsequently, the concentration of heavy metals in surface water holds significant importance, impacting both human health and the environment. In the study, we delved into the mean values of various heavy metals, such as Pb, Cd, Ni, Cr, and Mn, specifically focusing on the Alape River and its watershed. Surprisingly, these metals were BDL. However, when it came to Fe, the mean concentration was measured at 12.40 mg/L in the Alape River and 9.86 mg/L in its watershed. Similarly, Cu exhibited a mean concentration of 0.53 mg/L and 0.37 mg/L, while Zn showed a mean concentration of 0.67 mg/L and 0.25 mg/L, respectively (see Table 3). As we assess these figures, it becomes imperative to compare them against the recommended limits set by various regulatory bodies. According to the NSDWQ [51], Fe, Cu, and Zn should not exceed 0.3 mg/L, 1.0 mg/L, and 3.0 mg/L, respectively. The WHO [53] provides slightly different limits, stating that Fe, Cu, and Zn should remain below 0.3 mg/L, 2.0 mg/L, and 5.0 mg/L, respectively. Meanwhile, the NESREA [51] suggests limits of 0.3 mg/L, 1.5 mg/L, and 3.0 mg/L for Fe, Cu, and Zn, respectively (see Table 3). Examining the results in light of these guidelines, it is observed that Fe exceeds the recommended limits set by regulatory bodies, while Cu and Zn remain within the acceptable range. This high concentration of

Fe could potentially be attributed to mining activities in the study area. Interestingly, other studies conducted worldwide on heavy metal concentrations in surface waters reported similar values of Fe, Cu, and Zn. A study conducted in the Gomti River, India, revealed Fe values ranging from 0.72 to 1.69 mg/L [10], which falls below the levels observed in this study. Likewise, a study conducted in the Han River, South Korea, showed mean Cu and Zn concentrations of 3.9 and 280 mg/L, respectively [69], surpassing the findings from this study. Further exploration of the data uncovered that the control point in the Alape River recorded Fe value of 6.90 mg/L, surpassing the recommended limits by the regulatory bodies, while Pb, Cu, Cd, Ni, Cr, Mn, and Zn remained BDL (see Table 3). These findings emphasize the criticality of monitoring heavy metal levels in the Alape River and its watershed to ensure they align with the permissible limits stipulated by regulatory authorities. This vigilance is essential not only to safeguard the water body but also to protect public health. According to the WHO [53], the presence of high concentrations of heavy metals in water can lead to gastrointestinal disorders, liver and kidney damage, as well as respiratory problems. With this in mind, continuous monitoring and effective measures must be taken to maintain the safety of the water body and uphold public well-being.

Table 4: Chemical parameters for sediment quality in comparison to regulatory standards

Parameters	ARD Mean Values	AWD Mean Values	NESREA Limit for Sediment
Chemical Parameters			
pH	6.56 ± 0.143	6.83 ± 0.328	6.5 - 8.5
SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg/kg)	1.72 ± 0.130	1.86 ± 0.072	200
PO ₄ ³⁻ (mg/kg)	2.13 ± 0.523	2.75 ± 0.595	10
NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/kg)	3.26 ± 0.484	3.60 ± 0.410	100
TOC (%)	4.67 ± 0.786	6.33 ± 0.938	2%

The sediments collected from the Alape River and its surrounding watershed have revealed some findings. Upon analysis, it was discovered that the mean pH value of the river itself is 6.56, while the watershed registers a slightly higher pH of 6.83 (see Table 4). These results imply that both the river and its surrounding watershed maintain a very weak acidic environment. The significance of these pH values becomes apparent when we consider the recommended pH limits for sediment established by NESREA [51], falling between 6.5 and 8.5. Thus, the pH values observed in the sediments of the Alape River and its watershed align with the guidelines. To gain a broader perspective; we can compare these findings to other published studies. Notably, a study conducted in the Ona River, located in Ibadan, Nigeria, reported a mean pH value of 6.52 in their sediment samples [9]. Remarkably, this

aligns closely with the pH values obtained from the sediment samples of the Alape River and its watershed. Such consistency across different Nigerian rivers underscores the relevance and reliability of the findings from this study. Delving deeper into the composition of the sediments, it was observed find that the acidic nature of the sediment in the Alape River and its watershed can be attributed to the presence of carbonate, silicates, phosphates, and free hydroxyl ions. These elements contribute to the overall weak acidity observed in the sediments. While these findings provide valuable insights into the current state of the Alape River, it is crucial to emphasize the necessity of continuous monitoring. In addition, the values for the parameters, pertaining to Alape River and its watershed, reflect crucial insights into the sediment composition. Notably, the sediments exhibited relatively low

concentrations of SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} , and NO_3^- . Specifically, the mean value for SO_4^{2-} stood at 1.72 mg/kg and 1.86 mg/kg, while the mean value for PO_4^{3-} measured 2.13 mg/kg and 2.75 mg/kg. Additionally, the mean value for NO_3^- amounted to 3.26 mg/kg and 3.60 mg/kg, respectively, for both Alape River and its watershed (see Table 4). To establish the significance of these findings, it is essential to consider the recommended limits set by NESREA [51]. According to their guidelines, the acceptable limits for sediment should not exceed 200 mg/kg, 10 mg/kg, and 100 mg/kg for SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} , and NO_3^- , respectively. Comparatively, the values obtained from this study comfortably fell well below these established limits, further emphasizing the favourable sediment quality (see Table 4). Moreover, the results obtained from this study align harmoniously with the previous research conducted on sediment quality in various Nigerian rivers. These authors observed a concentration range for SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} , and NO_3^- spanning from 0.07 to 17.45 mg/kg, 0.04 to 21.0 mg/kg, and 0.06 to 57.80 mg/kg, respectively [4,11]. Remarkably, these findings complement the outcome of our study, collectively indicating that the sediments remain untainted by the presence of these pollutants. Consequently, the analysis of sediment samples extracted from the Alape River, and its watershed reveals a noteworthy presence of organic matter, as indicated by the mean TOC of 5.26%. Interestingly, this value surpasses the NESREA [51] limit of 2% set for TOC in sediment (see

Table 4). To contextualize these findings, it is worthwhile to refer to a study conducted in Warri, Nigeria which reported TOC value ranging from 0.14% to 2.56% in sediment samples collected from the Mangrove swamp [5]. Significantly, the TOC concentration observed in the Alape River and its watershed lies above the reported range in the literature. It is crucial to recognize that elevated levels of organic matter in sediments can have detrimental effects on the aquatic ecosystem, leading to eutrophication, hypoxia, and potentially harming aquatic life. However, it is imperative to interpret the TOC concentrations within the broader context of other factors, such as sediment grain size, hydrodynamics, and land use activities, as highlighted in some literatures [7]. Considering these variables will provide a more comprehensive understanding of the implications of the observed TOC levels in the sediments.

The mean TPH values in sediment from Alape River and its watershed were observed to be 0.58 mg/kg and 0.65 mg/kg, respectively, falling within the DPR [52] recommended TPH limit of 50 mg/kg in sediment (See Table 5). These findings are significant because they indicate that the levels of TPH in the area are relatively low, suggesting a lack of widespread hydrocarbon contamination. This aligns with a study conducted in south-western Nigeria where they reported similarly low TPH concentrations ranging from 0.116 mg/kg to 0.146 mg/kg in sediments from the Ugbo waterway [70]. By

connecting these studies, it becomes apparent that the sediments from Alape River and its watershed exhibit comparable high TPH concentrations to those found in the Ugbo waterway. Such consistency reinforces the notion that hydrocarbon contamination is not prevalent in the

region. Furthermore, it is worth noting that PAHs in the sediment from Alape River and its watershed was BDL (see Table 5). Overall, these findings are encouraging, as they suggest that the Alape River and its watershed are relatively free from significant petroleum-related pollutants.

Table 5: Hydrocarbons and heavy metals parameters for sediment quality in comparison to regulatory standards

Parameters	ARD Mean Values	AWD Mean Values	NESREA Limit for Sediment	DPR Limit for Sediment
Hydrocarbons and Heavy Metals Parameters				
TPH (mg/kg)	0.58 ± 0.155	0.65 ± 0.118	50	50
PAHSs (mg/kg)	BDL	BDL	40	40
Fe (mg/kg)	4348.89 ± 1752.346	1727.40 ± 792.88	5000	-
Pb (mg/kg)	1.65 ± 2.121	0.49 ± 0.790	35	-
Cu (mg/kg)	1.53 ± 1.453	1.37 ± 0.252	100	-
Cd (mg/kg)	BDL	BDL	5	-
Ni (mg/kg)	BDL	BDL	140	-
Cr (mg/kg)	BDL	BDL	20	-
Mn (mg/kg)	20.65 ± 17.434	12.91 ± 1.715	200	-
Zn (mg/kg)	21.13 ± 5.231	14.33 ± 2.596	300	-

(-) = Not Applicable

Furthermore, the heavy metal results from sediment in Alape River and its watershed showed that Cd, Ni, and Cr were BDL, indicating minimal presence of these metals in the sediments (see Table 5). However, the mean values of Fe in the sediment collected from the study area were found to be 4,348.89 mg/kg and

1,727.40 mg/kg, respectively, falling below the recommended limit of 5,000 mg/kg set by NESREA. Fe is an essential mineral for human health, but when present in high concentrations, it can become toxic and can lead to various health issues, including anaemia, liver damage, and neurological problems, as highlighted by WHO

[53]. Interestingly, the values of Fe in the sediments from the Alape River and its watershed were higher compared to other studies conducted on rivers in Nigeria. A study conducted in Benue, Nigeria reported Fe concentrations ranging from 137.43 to 146.48 mg/kg in sediment collected from the River Benue [71]. This suggests that the Alape River and its watershed are significantly affected by natural sources of iron or human activities such as mining, in comparison to other rivers in Nigeria. On the other hand, the mean values of Pb in the sediment from the Alape River and its watershed were 1.65 mg/kg and 0.49 mg/kg, respectively, which fall below the recommended limit of 35 mg/kg set by NESREA [51] (see Table 5). The levels of Pb in the sediment samples collected from the Alape River were notably lower compared to concentrations reported in other studies conducted on rivers in Nigeria. A study on River Abesan and Owo reported Pb concentrations ranging from 84.16 to 204.11 mg/kg in sediment samples from those rivers [4]. This suggests that the Alape River and its watershed are not significantly impacted by lead pollution when compared to other rivers in Nigeria.

Similarly, the mean values of Cu in sediment from the Alape River and its watershed was 1.53 mg/kg and 1.37 mg/kg, respectively, which is below the recommended limit of 100 mg/kg set by NESREA [51] (see Table 5). The values of Cu in the sediment samples from the study area was found to be higher when compared to those

reported in other studies conducted on rivers in Nigeria. A study on Ona River in Ibadan, Nigeria, reported Cu value ranging from 0.38 to 0.41 mg/kg in sediment from the river [9]. This suggests that the Alape River and its watershed are not significantly affected by Cu pollution in comparison to other rivers in Nigeria. Moreover, the mean values of Mn in sediment from the Alape River and its watershed were 20.65 mg/kg and 12.91 mg/kg which is significantly lower than the recommended limit of 200 mg/kg set by NESREA [51] (see Table 5). The values of Mn in the sediments from the study area fell within the range reported in other studies conducted on rivers in Nigeria. A study on the Jare River in Katsina, Nigeria reported Mn concentrations ranging from 17.63 to 66.72 mg/kg in sediment samples [72]. This suggests that the Alape River and its watershed may be significantly affected by natural sources of manganese or human activities such as mining.

Finally, the mean values of Zn in sediment from the Alape River and its watershed was 21.13 mg/kg and 14.33 mg/kg which is significantly lower than the recommended limit of 300 mg/kg set by NESREA [51] (see Table 5). The Zn value in the sediment from the study area is similar to the values reported in other studies conducted on rivers in Nigeria. A study of sediments from selected dams in Katsina, Nigeria, reported Zn values ranging from 5.55 to 19.95 mg/kg [8]. These findings indicate that the Alape River and

its watershed are not heavily impacted by Zn pollution.

CONCLUSION

Most of the results obtained from the analysis of surface water and sediment from Alape River and its watershed in Igbokoda, South-West Nigeria fell within regulatory benchmark with the exception of BOD, COD, TOC and Fe. The results show a comprehensive picture of the water quality and potential environmental impacts. The water quality, while generally acceptable for industrial and agricultural activities, requires treatment before human and domestic consumption. However, ongoing monitoring, further research, and the establishment of preventive measures are crucial to safeguard against potential pollution risks, especially in the event of industrialization in the area.

The findings of this study provide valuable baseline data for future investigations, supporting the implementation of effective measures to protect the water body and surrounding ecosystem. By prioritizing environmental preservation and sustainable practices, we can ensure the long-term health and well-being of the Alape River and its watershed, fostering a harmonious coexistence between human activities and the natural environment.

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